

Educational Leadership Competencies: Efforts to Create a School Culture of Character

Shindy Lestari¹, Tri Ulfa², Farah Alfian Ghofar Rahmat³, Khasbi Ainun Najib⁴

^{1,2,4}(State Islamic University Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta, Indonesia)

³(State University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: Efforts to realize a school culture of character, first a leader who shows the example of leadership of his character and has positive competence both in terms of personality, managerial, entrepreneurship, supervision and social. This research uses descriptive methods with a qualitative approach. The study sample consisted of 1 principal and 15 IT elementary school teachers Raudhaturrahmah Pekanbaru. This research aims as a study material and provides information about educational leadership that has competence will be able to make policies in accordance with the values of character and development of science and technology and efforts that can be made in realizing a school culture of character. The results of this study include: the cultivation of cultural values integrated in: 1) rules of order, 2) routine activities, 3) spontaneous activities, 4) transparency, 5) school literacy movements, 6) learning activities and 7) extracurricular activities. So it is very important that all stakeholders play an active role in trying to get used to instilling character values in order to become a school culture and form a complete personality in each individual.

KEYWORD: Leadership Competency Of Education, School Culture, Character

I. INTRODUCTION

The world of education must be able to play an active role in preparing educated human resources capable of facing various challenges of life both locally, regionally, nationally and internationally (Suyitno, 2017). There is much impact of globalization era and Information, Communication, and Technology on students' character. This will bring world progress to multicultural civilization leading to students being adaptable selectively with multicultural situation in order that they don't lose their identities. Character values should be integrated in school leading to positive student behavior (Marini, 2017).

In educational institutions that hold the highest position of leadership is the principal with the obligation to have standards so that performance in leading can run effectively and efficiently and can understand and solve various problems that occur and be able to decide a wise decision. A leader is stipulated in the Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 6 of 2018 concerning the assignment of teachers as principals.

School institutions are educational organizations that have a culture where it grows and develops from the behavior, mindset of school residents and communities. Thus, school culture is the most important concept in school institutions that aim to instill character values so as to shape the personality of school residents through ethics in order to become a complete character in the individual (Maisyaroh, et al, 2019).

However, the ever-evolving times make the character of the generation even more degenerate towards violation of norms. The issue of character has raised global discussion in society these days, so it is essential to define the

term. In simple terms, Character can be defined as good personal qualities, such as knowing goodness, willingness to do good things, having good behavior, originating from thought, heart, physical, psychological, and mental aspects (Suherman, 2018; Hastuti, et al, 2019; Mukhtar & Dallyono, 2020). According to Samani and Hariyanto (in Fahrilyani, et al, 2019) stated that the implementation of character education in Indonesia is very important and should be implemented as early as possible. The problem is seen from violations of norms such as fighting between students, low generational morale, violence, bullying, dominance between seniors and juniors, drug use and so on.

Along with the rise of moral and moral problems that hit the world of education, the emphasis on the realization of character education is very important (Nashihin, 2018). According to Annurahman (2021) stated that the phenomenon of weakening character can be seen easily both directly in the daily life of society, as well as through various media. This phenomenon also touches school life, especially in students at various levels and educational units have increasingly shown improvement in recent times.

In preventing and minimizing problems, it is very important for the principal to lead and run the school institution management system. Therefore, the principal must have the competencies contained in Permendikbud No. 6 of 2018 consisting of personality competence, managerial competence, entrepreneurial competence, supervising competence and social competence. Competent principals can strive in implementing school culture of character by involving all school residents.

Character education as an effort to create a generation of character who is able to face the development and demands of the times in accordance with the norm. Therefore, through character education it is expected that generations have faith and piety to God Almighty, noble practice, have academic competence. Thus character education is expected to become a school culture (Isbadrianingtyas and Suwandayani, 2017).

The character of a cultured person will be seen from behavior that is in accordance with character values, according to Rahayu (2016) argues that in the formation of character values of learners, stakeholders have a very important role such as school, family and community. Therefore, the urgency to build the character of citizens through education must continue to be maximized, because through good character, the possibility of a cultured nation and state can be realized (Saputra & Budimansyah, 2021). So that the development of student character values, 21st century literacy culture has an active and creative role, which encourages students to participate in planning, implementation and evaluation using learning technology (Novitasari, et al, 2019).

Based on this background, it is very important for the principal to strive to create a school culture of character by planning, evaluating, developing character education and curriculum development, learning, military management, learning facilities and resources, finance, service to students, establishing cooperation with the community while creating a positive climate in the school. Therefore, this research aims as a study material as well as providing alternative educational leadership solutions in making efforts to create a school culture of character.

II. METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative methods with a descriptive approach that is naturalistic research, this is because the research is done in a natural setting, then the collected data is analyzed qualitatively (Sugiyono, 2016: 14). Researchers consider qualitative methods because it is relevant to describe the conditions that occur at this time so that it can be a solution material in making efforts to create a school culture of character.

This type of data in this study is primary data with data collection techniques in the form of interviews and online questionnaires distributed to research samples. While the subject and object of this study are the principal and 15 teachers of IT Elementary School Raudhaturrahmah Pekanbaru. This research sampling technique uses purposive sampling and research instruments used, consisting of interview guidelines conducted online through the WhatsApp application to the headmaster of IT elementary school and interviews and online questionnaires in the form of google form distributed to 15 IT elementary school teachers Raudhaturrahmah. Can be seen in the chart as following:

Chart 1. Research Flow

III. RESULT

Assessment of Principal Competency

Leadership held by the principal is required to have the competencies contained in Permenduknas Number 28 of 2010 Article 1 on The Standard of Principal / Madrasah, namely knowledge, attitude and skills in the dimensions of personality competence, manjerial competence, entrepreneurial competence, supervision competence and social competence.

Based on the results of the analysis of research data by disseminating online questionnaires to 15 IT Elementary Teachers Raudhaturrahmah who aim to assess the competence of principals in an effort to create a school culture of character, obtained research results, among others:

1. Personality Competence

Graphic 1. Personality Competence

In the graph above, results obtained from online questionnaires show that the personality competence of the principal is in the category is very good with a score of 60% and a good category with a score of 40%. So this shows that the principal has a personality in accordance with the personality competencies contained in Permendiknas Number 13 of 2007.

In this study, indicators developed into the item of statement on the online kuisoner are personality competencies with noble attitudes and behaviors, have integrity, be open, able to control themselves, have talents and interests as leaders and are able to manage facilities and infrastructure.

The principal must have personality competence, it can give success to his leadership, a good leader is from someone who has a good personality as well. Thus the principal can carry out every function and duty to achieve educational goals.

2. Managerial Competence

Graphic 2. Managerial Competence

The results of the data obtained in the graph above show that the managerial competence of the principal obtained an excellent category with a score of 53%, a good category with a score of 27% and a fairly good category with a score of 20%. It can be concluded that the principal plays an important role in carrying out managerial competencies. Therefore, the managerial competence of a good principal will be able to improve the culture of a good school as well, so that it becomes a character for all school residents.

The quarter statement in this study was developed from indicators of the managerial competence of the principal, namely: a) planning, b) organizing, c) implementation and d) supervision. In accordance with Permendiknas Number 13 of 2007 on the managerial ability of the principal is: a) planning school activities, b) developing and leading the organization in optimal utilization of Human Resources, c) establish positive relationships with the community to support, finance schools and learning resources and manage in the framework of admission and capacity building of learners, d) manage school-specific service units to support decision-making activities and programs, e) utilize ict progress as an improvement in learning and school management and f) monitor, evaluate, and report the implementation of school program activities with appropriate procedures, and plan the follow-up.

3. Entrepreneurial Competence

Graphic 3. Entrepreneurial Competence

Based on the results on the graph that shows that the competence of the principal obtained a score of 34% with a very good category, while for the good category with a score of 53% and 13% with a fairly good category. This shows that the assessment of teachers to the entrepreneurial competence of the principal is in accordance with his ability and implementation in making and carrying out tasks and functions.

This research indicator of entrepreneurial competence was developed from Permendiknas No. 13 of 2007 regarding entrepreneurial competence, among others: a) the principal is able to create innovations that are useful for school development, b) work hard to achieve school success as an effective learning organization, c) have a strong motivation to succeed in carrying out the main tasks and functions as school leaders, d) unyielding and always looking for the best solution in the face of obstacles faced by the school, e) have an entrepreneurial instinct in managing school production activities or services as a source of learning learners.

Thus, the principal who has an entrepreneurial tendency is expected to be able to organize and diversify resources to set up businesses or programs to advance the school. In addition to that, the principal is able to respond to the needs, wants and expectations of the community. In the development of entrepreneurial competence there are character values that are prioritized, namely spiritual values, independence, hard work, honesty, unyielding, innovative and creative and integrity and commitment.

4. Supervised Competence

Graphic 4. Supervised Competence

Based on the results of the data in the graph above regarding the supervisory competence of principals with a score of 60% of the category is very good, while the score of 27% of the good category and the score of 13% of the category is quite good. This shows that the competence of the principal's supervision is measured from the competency indicator which is the ability of the principal in planning an academic supervision program in order to improve the teacher's professional, carry out academic supervision of teachers using appropriate supervision approaches and techniques, follow up on the results of academic supervision of teachers in order to improve teacher professionalism.

Principals who have supervising competence carry out their duties in supervising and together with teachers in carrying out and improving various efforts in the learning process. One therefore, supervision is an effort by a principal in coaching so that teachers can improve the quality of their teaching through planning measures, real teaching appearances and making changes in a rational way in an effort to improve student learning outcomes and educational goals. Cultures can be transformed by interactions between leaders and staff with focus on visions, goals and shared ideas of ideal behaviors or sometimes also by leaders building an infrastructure promoting change (Ostroff et al., 2013; Nehez and Blossing, 2020).

Psychologically the supervised activities carried out by the principal will affect the performance of teachers. The satisfaction felt by teachers is due to the principal being able to carry out supervision activities well, thus increasing the motivation of teachers to carry out their duties so as to achieve goals and improve the quality of education.

5. Social Competence

Graph 5. Social Competence

The results of the online questionnaire in the graph above showed the social competence of the principal in kagetori very well with a score of 87%, while the good category with a score of 13%. Indicators developed to measure the social competence of the principal include the efforts of the principal in increasing cooperation with other parties for the benefit of the school, then participating in social activities and having social agreements with others.

The results of the study were measured based on the indicators contained in Permendiknas No. 13 of 2007 that the social competence of the principal is able to cooperate with other parties for the benefit of the school, participate in community social activities, have social sensitivity to other people or groups.

In accordance with Mulyasa (in Yuliawati and Enas, 2018) argues that there are seven social competencies that must be possessed by the principal, namely: a) have knowledge of social and religious customs. b) Have knowledge of culture and traditions. c) Have knowledge of the core of democracy. d) Have knowledge of aesthetics. e) Have knowledge of appreciation and social awareness. f) Have the right attitude towards knowledge and work and g) have loyalty to human dignity and dignity.

Thus it can be understood that the principal has social competence towards all stakeholders. The important role of social competence lies in two things, namely: 1) the personal role of the principal who lives in the middle of the community that a principal needs to have the ability to blend with the community, this ability includes the ability to blend politely, flexible with the community.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Efforts to Create a School Culture of Character

School culture is a set of values that underlie the behaviors, traditions, daily habits and symbols practiced by school residents. According to Deal and Peterson quoted by Rahmat and Suharto (in Labudasari and Rochmah, 2018) it is argued that the concept of school-based management consists of behavioral values, traditions, daily habits, and symbols practiced by principals, teachers, officers, administration, learners, and the community around the school. So that the school is responsible not only to print learners who excel in science and technology, but also in character and personality, it can be supported by the school culture.

A character school culture needs to be done early on and accustomed to elementary school age. The potential that is good if humans are accustomed from birth, but in realizing the positive potential there needs to be habituation in the cultivation of values both from family, school and community. Therefore, the first step in the cultivation of character values is to realize together and unite the view that it is very important to integrate character values in all activities so that they can become habits by all stakeholders.

Indicators in measuring school culture are: a) relationships between personnel, b) norms and rules, c) habits, d) attitudes or behaviors. Thus the strengthening of school culture-based character education focuses on habituation and cultural formation in representing the main values of the character that is a priority. Character education is integrated into various educational programs and activities in the education unit by making efforts using a comprehensive approach.

Planting character values in the school environment is required in all learning activities and other routine activities by integrating in character education programs. Thus character education is a joint effort of all school residents to realize and create a culture in the school, namely character culture. The cultivation and habituation of character education in schools through the educational environment can be implemented directly or indirectly and finally a school culture is formed as seen from the implementation of all stakeholders (Curriculum Center in Supraptaningrum and Agustin, 2015).

The advantage of school institutions is to have a strong school culture and still exist. A school must have a mission to create a school culture that is characterful, challenging and fun, fair, creative, integrated, and indicative to the achievement of vision, produce graduates who are high quality in their intellectual development and have a character of piety, honest, creative, able to be role models, work hard, tolerant and capable in leading, in addition to being able to answer the challenges of human resource development needs that can play a role in development of science and technology and based on IMTAQ.

The research conducted aims as a study material as well as providing solutions on educational leadership competencies in making efforts to create a school culture of character. So that it can answer the formulation of the problem by knowing what efforts are made and implemented by all school residents. Researchers conducted an interview with the principal of Raudhaturrahmah Integrated Islamic Elementary School using an interview consisting of seven questions, the results of the interview, as follows:

1. Rules of Order

Rules of order are made as a form of provisions to be obeyed by all school residents, namely: a) principals, teachers and students enter the school on time. b) All students wear uniforms in accordance with the provisions of the school day, if anyone violates without a good reason it will be sanctioned, this emphasizes constructive discipline. c. If the student does not attend the school, the student's parents or the representative attach a certificate with the actual evidence. d) All school residents must maintain the environment, maintain cleanliness and neatness. e) All school residents must maintain school order as a form of mutual respect and respect between each other. f) All school residents are required to take care of their own belongings, others and the school.

From the provisions of the rules of order that apply in SD IT Raudhaturrahmah aims in instilling character values such as discipline, self-respect, respect, environmental care, social care and responsibility. According to Mahardika, et al, (2020) in his research states that the culture developed in schools can foster a disciplined attitude. Students become human beings who are full of optimism, dare to perform, behave cooperatively, and have a sense of responsibility. So that school culture is one of the important things to improve the quality of schools and the quality of a country.

2. Routine Activities

Routine activities are activities that students do continuously and consistently at all times. For example: a) Monday ceremony activities, this is required to students as the executor of ceremonial activities by providing opportunities to each class, ranging from grade IV to class VI. b) Friday religious activities such as reading the

Qur'an or Q.S. Yasin together as a form of religious character cultivation. c) Gymnastics activities on Saturdays are carried out as a form of refreshment for all school residents, in this case aimed at all citizens concerned with self-health. d) Perform religious holiday ceremonies that are usually done by preaching together, gathering infaq and making a race that is nuanced Islamic.e) Examination of body hygiene, class picket, sunnah Dhuha congregational prayer and Dzuhur and Ashar congregational prayers. f) The entire class is lined up before entering the class. g) Pray before and after lessons, pray together before starting learning. h) Say hello when meeting teachers, educators, and friends. i) In addition to that activities carried out such as agile (plant flush movement), resounding (movement of seeing, taking, discarding) and echoes (healthy eating movement).

From the routine activities that apply in SD IT Raudhaturrahmah aims in instilling character values such as religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, self-respect, respect, friendship, cooperation, peace love, environmental care, social care and responsibility.

3. Spontaneous Activities

Activities carried out by learners spontaneously at that time, for example, collect donations when there are friends affected by disaster or donations to the community when disaster strikes. This spontaneous activity is carried out as a form of planting character values such as religious, tolerance, democracy, national spirit, love of the homeland, respect, respect, friendship, cooperation, peace-loving, environmental care, social care and responsibility.

4. Exemplary

Exemplary is shown from the principal as a school leader as an example for teachers and students. Instead, all school residents should set a good example of example. Like the condition of clean toilets, the provision of trash cans in accordance with the category is organic and inorganic, creating a green environment and courtyard by planting flowers and trees on Saturdays that can be done twice a month, displaying posters of wise words in the school hallway and in the classroom and civilizing the 5S (smile, greeting, greeting, courtesy and courtesy).

The activities are carried out as a form of planting character values such as religious, honest, tolerance, hard work, creative, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love of the homeland, respect, friendly / communicative respect, peace love, environmental care, social care, responsibility.

5. School Literacy Movement

The school literacy movement is carried out in three stages, namely: activities are carried out with 1) the habituation stage is done by providing literacy books and all students read books for 15 minutes before starting learning, then the teacher and students provide material rich in text in each class. In addition, the school provides libraries, reading corners, school reading areas, posters on the benefits of reading so that students are motivated to read. 2) The development stage is that there are various collections of enrichment books that vary in the form of non-fiction and fiction, then teachers and students conduct activities in response to reading, as well as activities that appreciate literacy achievements.3) The stage of learning, the existence of activities to respond to reading for example one student is asked to read and other students listen to the reading, in addition to that the teacher can ask students to find the meaning, message or intent of the reading in accordance with the student's understanding, in this case also trained reading strategies to improve the understanding of learners.

The activities of the school literacy movement are carried out as a form of planting character values such as tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, respecting achievement, respect, communicative, reading, social care and responsibility.

6. Learning Activities

Learning and teaching concepts designed by teachers that associate teaching material with real-world situations or things close to students. So that students are able to make connections between the knowledge they have and its application in their lives. Therefore, syllabus, RPP, and teaching materials are designed so that the content and learning activities are character education insight.

Examples of values instilled in the learning process in the preliminary activities include teachers coming on time then the value instilled is discipline, praying before opening the lesson, then the value instilled is religious, the teacher checks the presence of students then the values instilled are discipline and other character values.

In the minimum preliminary activity steps that must be met is orientation, perception, motivation and giving reference to students, then the core learning activities are divided into three stages, namely: a) exploration that involves learners by applying independent values, logical thinking, creative, cooperation, hard work, mutual respect, caring for the environment, confidence, curiosity, manners, b) the elaboration stage where teachers familiarize learners with instilling the value of love of science, creative, logical, confident, critical, mutual respect, courtesy, cooperation, mutual respect, responsibility, (honest, disciplined, hard work, and c) the confirmation stage is a step that can be done by giving positive feedback and reinforcement in the form of oral, written, cue, or reward to the success of learners, then the value instilled is mutual respect, curiosity, confidence, manners, critical, logical, understanding the advantages, shortcomings of oneself, caring.

As well as closing activities, namely the stages of activities carried out, among others, teachers together with learners and or themselves make summaries / conclusions of lessons. At this stage, the values instilled are independent, cooperation, critical, logical, mutual respect, confidence and courtesy.

7. Extracurricular Activities

Extracurricular activities as a form of character development such as extracurricular tambourine and art and memorization of the Qur'an are carried out on Fridays after school and extracurricular scouting, music, karate, drum bands, pencak silat, chess performed on the Saturday after school.

Planting character values in extracurricular such as religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love of the homeland, respect and respect, cooperation, friendly / communicative , peace-loving, fond of reading, caring for the environment, social care and responsibility.

B. Educational Leadership Competence: Efforts to Create a School Culture of Character

The character education process needs to be done early on and must be maximized at primary school age. Good potential has actually been owned by humans since birth, but the potential must continue to be fostered and developed through socialization from both family, school, and community (Rahmawati and Annisa, 2020). Therefore, the first step in implementing character education is to instill common awareness and equalize perceptions of the importance of integrating character values in all activities so that these values can become habits by all stakeholders (Salim in Evanada, et al., 2018).

As a learning leader the principal must understand that aspects of the mind and cognition and memory of students are something that goes beyond the physical aspect (extending beyond the skin) so that the learning process in strengthening student character is to turn on the intermental and extramental functions in culture (Rahmawati, et al, 2020). The competent principal in accordance with the decree No. 13 of 2007 will be able to make policies and programs to create a character school culture for all school residents, namely:

1. Personality Competence

Policies and programs made at the same time are also implemented by the principal and all school residents in creating a school culture of character that is a principal able to set an example and familiarize themselves in accordance with positive character values, such as instilling disciplinary values, hard work and responsibility. If a principal wants all school residents to instill the values of discipline, hard work and responsibility, then the first person to be used as an example is the principal, so that it will have an impact on all school residents both staff, teachers, students and other school officials.

2. Managerial Competence

Managerial competencies possessed by the principal will have a positive influence on the efforts made by the principal in improving the quality of the school so that the achievement of national education goals is achieved. Various policies are planned so that it becomes a program that is implemented together to integrate the planting of character values, such as planting a hundred trees every three months. This is done by the principal as a form of creating a conducive and innovative school climate and culture and aims that all school residents have the character of respect, respect, environmental care and responsibility.

3. Enterpreniourial Competence

The entrepreneurial competence of the principal will be seen from the ability of the principal in reading, understanding the opportunities by making policies aimed at floating the human resources of the school's citizens. It requires the principal to create an innovation, work hard, have motivation and unyielding.

Efforts are made to create a school culture of character such as creating programs for school residents both teachers and students can be creative with recycled used goods so that they become an item or craft that has selling value. The values of character are instilled, namely discipline, hard work, creative, independent, curiosity, friendly / communicative, environmental care, social care and responsibility.

4. Supervised Competence

Supervision competence is very mandatory for a leader, it aims so that the principal can make a policy with training to develop teacher potential that will have a positive effect on the quality of performance and teacher activities in class learning. In addition, the principal is able to help teachers conduct critical evaluations of work activities, learning problems, and help plan improvements. At the same time increase awareness of teachers and other school officials towards democratic ways of working in accordance with the mutually agreed school culture, as well as the willingness to help. It aims as the cultivation of character values in the school environment and in the classroom that reflect the values of Religion, Pancasila, culture and national education.

5. Social Competence

A leader must have good social competence wherever he is, it is a reflection of himself as a leader who holds the values of norms. Therefore, the policy made by the principal by civilizing the 5S will have a positive impact, so that it becomes a complete character for each individual school citizen.

The cultivation of character values is done with character education for all school residents who contain components of knowledge, awareness or will, and actions to carry out these values. Efforts are made to be carried out effectively by affirming the components of education itself, namely the content of the curriculum, the learning and assessment process, handling or management of subjects, school management, implementation of co-curricular activities or activities, empowerment of infrastructure facilities, financing, and work ethic of all school / environment residents. Indicators to measure schools of character are by paying attention to the relationship between personnel, this is because it is very important for all school residents to interact well. In

addition, the principal must make policies and programs that are tailored to the norms and regulations made must be carried out by all school residents with commitment. According to Ariaah, et al (2018) stated that the school is a means of formation and character development of students who require special attention, such as the presence of professional teachers, curriculum taught, a conducive environment, the learning process that contains character values, and school culture.

In addition, character education is interpreted as a behavior of school residents who in organizing education must be of character. Activities carried out by integrating positive character values, thus creating individuals able to behave or behave in accordance with character values that are useful to themselves, family, school and society. Thus character education is very important for learners. The existence of character education values for learners forms the good character they need in life (Wardani, et al, 2020). The key to one's success is the value of attitudes related to Almighty God, ourselves, others, the environment and the nationality that will come into attitudes, paradigms, feelings, speech, good actions (based on norms, laws, customs and cultures) (Abbas and Zainudin, 2014).

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research it can be concluded that the principal who is competent both in terms of personality competence, managerial, entrepreneurship, supervision and social will be able to create and regulate the management system of an educational institution by influencing human resources in an organization to move or follow orders in accordance with common goals. So that principals who have personality, managerial, entrepreneurial, supervising and social competencies will be able to make efforts to create a school culture of character by instilling and familiarizing character values for all school residents and stakeholders, such as: making policies in orderly regulations, school routine activities, spontaneous activities, transparency, development of school literacy movements, learning activities and extracurricular activities. It will be able to be realized effectively and efficiently in accordance with the objectives of national education.

REFERENCE

- [1] Annurahman. Implementation Of Character Education In Building School Culture. *Jurnal Visi Ilmu Pendidikan*. 13(1), 2021, 11-23, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26418/jvip.v13i1.44565>.
- [2] Ariaah, F. Jalal, A. Supena. Evaluation of School Culture In Character Building at Ummul Quro Elementary School in Bogor, Indonesia. *International Journal of Advances in Scientific Research and Engineering*. 4(7), 2018, 236-239, doi: <http://doi.org/10.31695/IJASRE.2018.32785>.
- [3] A. Kurniawati, I. Suntoro and H. Yanzi. Pengaruh Iklim Dan Budaya Sekolah Terhadap Sikap Disiplin Siswa SMP Negeri 3. *Jurnal Kultur Demokrasi*, 5(2), 2016, 12–22.
- [4] A. Marini. Integration of Character Values in School Culture at Elementary Schools in Jakarta, Indonesia. *Journal of Arts & Humanities*, 6(5), 2017, 21-32, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18533/journal.v6i5.1171>.
- [5] B. A. Mahardika, A. Kusna, D. R. Nugraheni, D. Eriyani, N. O. Yulindasari, S. Taftania, V. M. Sholihah, D. D. N. Benty. Building School Culture to Establish Students Character. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research: 1st International Conference On Information Technology And Education*. 508, 2020, 428-433.
- [6] B. I. Suwandayani, N. Isbadrianingtyas. Peran Budaya Sekolah Dalam Pembentukan Karakter Anak Sekolah Dasar. *Prosiding SENASGABUD: Seminar Nasional Lembaga Kebudayaan*, 2017, 34–41.
- [7] D. W. Rahayu. Internalisasi Nilai Karakter Melalui Budaya Sekolah. *Jurnal Buana Pendidikan*, 7(22), 2016, 49–68, doi: <https://doi.org/10.36456/bp.vol12.no22.a618>.
- [8] E. Labudasari and E. Rochmah. Peran Budaya Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Karakter Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pendidikan I, 1*, 2019, 19-27.

- [9] E. Yuliyawati. Implementasi Kompetensi Kepala Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Kompetensi Guru. *Indonesian Journal Of Education Management & Administration Review*, 2(2), 2018, 318–324, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4321/ijemar.v2i2.1930>.
- [10] Fahrilyani, Devita, Maisyaroh, and D. E. Kusumaningrum. Manajemen Pembinaan Karakter Peserta Didik Di Sekolah Dasar. *JAMP: Jurnal Adminitrasi Dan Manajemen Pendidikan*, 2(4), 2019, 204–212, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17977/um027v2i42019p204>.
- [11] F. Evananda, I. Bafadal and A. Y. Sobri. Studi Kasus Implementasi Pendidikan Karakter Pada Sekolah Dolan. *JAMP: Jurnal Adminitrasi Dan Manajemen Pendidikan*, 1(3), 2018, 255–262, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17977/um027v1i32018p252>.
- [12] H. Nashihin. Character Internalization Based School Culture of Karangmloko 2 Elementary School. *Abjadia: International Journal of Education*, 3(2), 2018, 81–90, doi: <https://doi.org/10.18860/abj.v3i2.6031>.
- [13] I. Suyitno. Development Of Cultural Literacy To Build Students' Character Through Learning. *Journal of Innovative Studies on Character and Education*. 1(1), 2017, 31-45.
- [14] J. Nehez and U. Blossing. Practices in different school cultures and principals' improvement work, *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2020.1759828>.
- [15] K. Abbas and Zainudin. Integrated Learning Model Cultural-Art And Character Education. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 2(8), 2014, 1-6.
- [16] M. Novitasari, Sutarna, S. Narimo and A. Fathoni. Promoting Literacy Culture and Character Education to form High-Level Thinking Students in Elementary School. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 4(9), 2019, 404-408.
- [17] M. N. Annisa, A. Wiliyah and N. Rahmawati. Pentingnya Pendidikan Karakter Pada Anak Sekolah Dasar Di Zaman Serba Digital. *Bintang: Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Sains*, 2(1), 2020, 35–48, doi: <https://doi.org/10.36088/bintang.v2i1.558>.
- [18] Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Nasional. Nomor 28 Tahun 2010 Tentang Penugasan Guru Sebagai Kepala Sekolah/Madrasah, Retrieved From <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=http://staff.unila.ac.id/radengunawan/files/2011/09/permendiknas-no.-28-tahun-20101.pdf&ved=2ahukewjf7ssx7l3tahvgfd4khwcybvq4chawmah6bagdeae&usq=aovvaw1dwb3ndxscfyehcvagnbuw>.
- [19] Peraturan Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan. Tentang Penugasan Guru Sebagai Kepala Sekolah. Retrieved From <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/138182/permendikbud-no-6-tahun-2018>.
- [20] S. R. Wardani, Andayani and Suyitno. Building Character Education in Elementary School Students through the Cultural-themed Literacy Book. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 4(1), 2020, 251-256.
- [21] Sugiyono. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2016).
- [22] Suprptiningrum and Agustini. Membangun Karakter Siswa Melalui Budaya Sekolah Di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter*, 6(2), 2015, 219–228, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21831/jpk.v0i2.8625>.
- [23] T. Muhtar and R. Dallyono. Character Education From The Perspectives Of Elementary School Physical Education Teachers. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 39(2), 2020, 395-408, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21831/cp.v39i2.30647>.
- [24] T. N. Rahmawati, M. Kharisma, H. Purwanto, Rusdinal and N. Gistituati. School Leadership Patterns in Character Value Strengthening in The First Middle School Country 34 Kerinci District. *International*

Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 21(1), 2020, 204-211. doi:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.52155/ijpsat.v21.1.1845>.

- [25] T. Saputra and D.Budimansyah. Strengthening Character Education Through School Culture in The New Normal Era: A Case Study at Al-Karim Lampung Basic Natural School. *Basic And Applied Education Research Journal*,2(1), 2021, 39–46, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/baerj.02.01.08>.